

IMPACT OF COVID-19 ON ADOLESCENT LEISURE ACTIVITIES: WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO SAARC COUNTRIES

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Abstract:

Today humanity is facing a serious threat in the form of a pandemic known as COVID-19, even adolescents the vital section of the youth population is affected by it. Psychologists believed leisure activities as an antecedent of the development of the adolescent. The objective of the study is to examine the change in adolescents' leisure activities, before lockdown (BLD) and after lockdown (ALD) due to this airborne disease.

The study is a cross-cultural study of 255 adolescents in the age group of (15-19) years studying in senior secondary classes in India and its neighboring countries Maldives and Bhutan is the part of the selected sample. The study used the questionnaire Leisure Interest Measure (LIM by Beard and Ragheb, 1980) and a structured key information schedule designed for studying smartphone usage patterns (SPUP) by teens. SPSS-23 and other statistical packages are used for analyzing the data to study the change in leisure activities. The results of the study are quite interesting and will be helpful in policy formulation related to adolescents' leisure activities. Serious research work should be conducted in this area, as it is a sensitive issue and requires more concentration after all adolescent is a valuable asset for any nation.

Keywords: COVID-19, Leisure Activities, Adolescent, Lock-down, Economy, Development

INTRODUCTION

An ancient Indian proverb holds that "the man who knows nothing of literature, music or art is nothing but a beast without the beast's tail and horns" (Basham, 1967: 384). Leisure activities in any country can easily be understood by visiting the historical monuments which are the rich cultural heritage of the country expressed the literature, art, paintings, sculptures, and folklores of the past time. Majumdar (1996) and Singh (2000) discuss how the cultural ideology and social structure of traditional Indian society defined leisure activities; the same concept will follow in the case of neighboring countries of India; Bhutan and Maldives.

The study specifically focused on adolescents and their leisure activities, so it's wise to discuss that. When children became teenagers they select their leisure activities according to their interests. Nowadays it is observed that adolescents' leisure activities are very much controlled by their peers i.e. the friend circle, they have joined in the school. It reflects that adolescents have to follow the rules of the group; otherwise, there is a fear of isolation, so it forced them to choose leisure activities according to the group.

Leisure activities supported by digital technology called '*Digital leisure*', quite popular amongst adolescence and their group members from their school or other schools. It is quite seen that close and old friends have created their specific group at WhatsApp, Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, Snap chat and at many other sites where they share their images, videos, messages, texting, spicy-gossips, notes, projects and even celebrating birthdays, examination-results, achievement parties and all

future activities planned at such platforms. Social networking sites are the medium through which, every new notification spreads among group members very easily. It is found that most of the time adolescents involved in screen activities, shows more interest in such activities rather than their studies or any other activities, it's a matter to think very seriously because there should be a balance in our daily life activities otherwise it will be a threat to various aspects of their life.

Leisure:

Leisure leads to subjective pleasure and objective happiness (Sylvester, 2005:2). Ancient Greek philosophers thought that leisure was a condition that *'supports the life of philosophy and thus cares for one's soul'* (Ildefonso, 2012: 32). Leisure activities were defined as non-productive activities which an individual pursue to enjoy their free time, these pursuits are quite different from their diurnal activities (Ragheb & Tate, 1993:62). "Leisure is an action that takes place at a given time, develops an identifiable activity and is perceived as a pleasant experience by the actor" (Kelly, 1982). From a philosophical point of view, leisure time defines as a segment of time that is used in social activities and maintaining the relationship between working time and social values (Shakirzyanova & Zakirova, 2019).

It has been seen that leisure activities are defined as free time, non-productive activities that are taken place for pleasure (Peter H. & Michael A., 1998 and Holder et al., 2009). Michael Argyle in his book *'The Social Psychology of Leisure'*, discussed ten kinds of leisure, first, five activities are mainly done at home; Watching T.V., Listening to Music, Reading Books, Social life and Hobbies whereas five activities are done mainly outside the home; Sports, Watching sports, Religious activities, Voluntary Work and Holidays and Tourism (pp.4-5). Planned leisure activities primarily focused on leisure engagement in such a way, keeping the view of entertainment and wellbeing (Kleiber, et al., 1986). Relaxed leisure are slack-time activities which take place for enjoyment with negligible demands such as socialising, reading magazines, listening to radio and music, watching television, etc. (Reed Larson and Douglas Kleiber, 1993), these activities never help anyone in inculcating any particular art or skills in an individual. Thus it is observed that leisure activity should be such which gives pleasure and happiness and will be responsible for the overall development of a child.

Adolescent and Leisure:

Psychologist believes that adolescence is the "second birth of man" this stage reflects the beginning of further life. Discussing young people's leisure and lifestyle, Shucksmith et al., 1993, focused that leisure needs are at solstice during adolescence. Adolescents have a lot of time for leisure, and their leisure activities have great importance in their life. Lanz et al., 1999, discussed that adolescence is a period of transition from childhood play to the era of adult struggles and realities. Adolescent's social life is the most central of their concerns; early in this period they make close friends with one or two of their sex, this develops into forming peer-group gangs or cliques, and it is the peer group culture that helps them become independent of home (Michael Argyle, 1996, p.56).

According to UNICEF, 2019 report, sixteen percent of the world's population are adolescents between the age group of 10-19 years which comprises 1.2 billion, it further suggests that nearly 350 million adolescents reside in South Asia which is comparatively populous than any other region in the world. It was observed that teenagers mostly spent their time in leisure pursuits than at study, for this, they gave excuses that they feel, their leisure pursuits are more satisfying than study; leisure gives them pleasure and happiness which promotes mental peace and physical health. This is not an exact reality because being a student we can't foresee our prime job. i.e. study, there should be a balance in one's life, everything has a proper place in daily life schedule and we can't forsake study for leisure, other activities have a secondary role in adolescent's life. Adolescents have to understand that leisure time is their free time apart from their studies and they have to manage it efficiently.

COVID-19 and Adolescent:

Adolescence is the most critical stage of life in which one attains knowledge, as well as expertise in cognitive skills, is very much affected by this lockdown which changed their lifestyle. To control the effects of COVID-19, as per the guidelines of WHO, the government of the concerned countries has taken the decision, to close the educational institutions worldwide, which affected the study as well as the physical and psychological status of youth (Nicola et al., 2020). According to UNESCO, as biological disasters spread out, nearly 107 countries worldwide implemented nationwide school closures, which impacted the study of 861.7 million children and youth, due to this they are out of school and it seems that their future is in the dark.

Adolescents have been facing mental and emotional disturbances, due to protracted closure of the educational institution, to retrench the effects of the pandemic, which affected their social relations with their peers. It is quite obvious that suicidal tendencies have been increased amongst adolescents along with other psychological problems like anxiety, anger, depression fear, stress, and many other mental problems due to the recent biological disaster, which is still active. (Md. Zahir A. et al., 2020 & Griffiths and Mamun, 2020).

COVID-19 is a great threat for human civilization especially for adolescents because since there is no such drug invented to get rid of such a pandemic, so physical distancing and wearing a mask are the best pills as directed by WHO, due to this peer interaction not possible as it is important for social development. This social distancing is distracting the mind of adolescents and now they are taking the help of digital technology for interacting with their peers. Poonam Muttreja (Executive . Director, PFI), says that "Due to COVID-19, adolescents are lockdown at their home which has increased the access of television and social media in their daily life; it harms their mental health". A recent study conducted by PFI found that nearly 46 percent of adolescents reported that they are spending more time online in social media activities during the lockdown. In a country like India, nearly 243 million, adolescents, lives are on the verge of great risk due to this pandemic (Gupta, P.,2020). Lockdown of educational institutions has made the lives of adolescents more difficult and many defiances arise beside them since they are not going to school, so they have full day leisure, *empty vessels make more sound*, so they are channelizing their energy in the wrong direction, most of their time they are busy on social networking sites, indulging in these activities they are spoiling their life and suffering from physiological and psychological problems.

An interview by MBA student Samuel Volkin at Johns Hopkins Center for Adolescent Health from Director Mr. T. Mendelson and Associate Director Mr. B. Marshall, Mendelson says that as schools are not operating, due to which adolescents are not getting chances of interacting with their friends' circle, as their requirements are quite different from others. Teenagers are at the stage of storm and stress when they give more importance to social relationships with their friends than any other relationship. The necessary guidelines issued by WHO and Gol, regarding coronavirus disease 2019; physical distancing of 6 feet, and proper hand wash time to time have a great influence on adolescents health. This pandemic period creates a big question in front of adolescents, how they can overcome such a problem? Marshall thinks that the developmental tasks of adolescents take place through interactions with peers. Schools are not just the educational centers but also the institution which inculcates ethics and values in an individual. "Adolescents depend on their mobile devices to connect with their friends, and it's more important for parents to help them use screen time in a good way rather than simply limiting its use" (Interview by S. Volkin- Director, Johns Hopkins Center for Adolescent Health, Baltimore).

LITERATURE REVIEW

The study by [Suman V. and Deepali S. \(2003\)](#) explore leisure activities of Indian adolescents across gender belongs to the middle class in urban and rural areas, boys enjoy more freedom to engage in outdoor activities, they spend their majority time with peers and have more opportunities for leisure and socialisation than girls, due to predefined role of gender socialisation of girls as homemakers and caregivers limits their public-based leisure activities, for reasons of safety as well as social image. Some of the studies explore that there is a positive correlation between social wellbeings and leisure activities like visiting families and friends, watching television, listening to radio and music, and playing sports and games ([Verena H.M. and Judith G. C., 1997](#); [Xiangyou, et al., 2010](#)). It has been observed in research studies that there has a positive linkage between leisure active engagement; psychological wellbeing and physical health ([Linda L.C., 2005](#)). It has been found in current studies that adolescents from Western industrialised countries like the USA, nearly 90% of them are consuming the internet throughout the day in various digital leisure activities involving online social activities and playing games ([Linda & Witt, 2011](#)).

The study conducted by [Andrew Lepp et al. \(2017\)](#), highlighted on leisure time cell phone use; users who are engaged less in mobile activities actively participate in physical activities like sports and games whereas those who are 'digitoholic', mostly engaged in screen activities, spend most of their time in online social activities including, chatting, video conferencing, emailing, texting, surfing and various other screen activities. [Chandrakanta J. & Akhand S. \(2021\)](#), the study focussed on leisure time activities of adolescents during pandemic COVID-19 and highlighted that adolescents spend most of their time on digital platforms. The study selected adolescents from India and Bhutan and studied the effects of leisure activities using digital technology and health problems faced by them. The result showed that initially when it studied the direct relation in absence of a mediator between independent (LIM) and dependent variable (Hlth_Prbl) existed a non-significant effect. There was no mediation effect of digital leisure between leisure interest measures and health problems. In general, it was observed that there was no difference in boys' and girls' social activities, but there was a difference in science and non-science students' digital leisure activities, which means the duration of time spent by them. Boys were more active on digital platforms than girls during the pandemic. It was found that boys on average 06-08 hours daily busy on social networking sites. Adolescents claimed health physical and psychological problems faced by them, headache and sleeping problems were quite common problems faced by most of the Indians. Indian adolescents were facing severe health problems in comparison to Bhutanese students as they were on average 3.5 hours less time engaged in online activities. The study claimed that Indian adolescents were at greater risk side than Bhutanese, either digitally or from a health point of view.

A study by [Iryna S. & Monika S. \(2015\)](#) focusing on family social leisure, examined the leisure participation of parents and their children, it was found that parents were friendly to their young children and they jointly actively participate in online social activities, even parents access the account of their kids and check it regularly to observe their online activities, it strengthens the love bond and trustworthiness among the family members. In the study by [Gürbüz Hatice et al. \(2017: 521\)](#) regarding screening activities between depressed and non-depressed adolescents, it was found that nearly 50% of both groups shows depressive symptoms, it was found out that depressed adolescents spend most of their time online activities and even they regularly check their status and tries to be online throughout the day, it reflects they have screen stressed, whereas non-depressed ones active online whenever it is needed.

During COVID-19, due to lockdown youths are unable to meet physically with their friends so they are taking the help of online social media for interacting with their near and dear ones, excessive use of these technologies affected their physical and mental health. Three leading researchers [Mimi Ito,](#)

Candice Odgers, and Stephen Schueller (2020) published the paper related to 'Youth Connectivity for Wellbeing', a review paper focused on how youth support each other with the help of digital technology, to overcome the problems of stress and lonesome. The study by Jamal A., 2020, on the usage of social media by teens during COVID-19, the paper disclose the facts of how online social media helps teens in enhancing skills, reducing anxiety and loneliness, most of the teens believed that being connected digitally helps them in social wellbeing (SWB), increasing confidence level, impulsion positive energy in their personality so that they can easily handle complex situations in their life.

JUSTIFICATION OF THE STUDY

According to the report global population by age (Jan 2019), it was found that 604 million 15-19 years (Simon Kemp, Global Digital Report, p.27), so study about adolescents is still a matter of great concern. Based on the previous study conducted so far, some of the studies focussed on SNS use among adults and college students, whereas some studies highlighted the relationship between mental health and duration of time spare on online networking sites. Some of the studies reported that no overt affinity exists amidst the duration of time spent on social networking sites and depression (Valdez J.D., et al. 2012; Jelenchick, et al., 2013; Simoncic, T. E., et al. 2014). Frequent studies were conducted on adolescents of Western countries in the case of Asian countries; Chinese and Korean adolescents have been a part of the study. In the case of a study conducted in India, where; Suman and Deepali, 2003 and Deshmukh, et al., 2014 studies highlighted the impact of SNS on the youth of India in both positive and negative ways, the study was carried out on youngsters between the age group of 18-29 years. Some of the other studies were also conducted in India but not so reliable through which one can draw inferences.

The understudy follows their instructions and moves ahead in this direction. Previously single study which has been conducted by the authors itself covered the adolescents of SAARC countries; India and Bhutan and studied their involvement in social activities using digital technology during the pandemic. The study is a mere attempt to examine the leisure activities of adolescents before and after lockdown due to COVID-19 and its impact on their physiological and psychological health. The study will explore various facts that are not yet explored and set up a benchmark for other researchers who are working in this field and even provide suggestions to parents, academicians, and the government of the concerned country to get rid of such a problem.

OBJECTIVES

The objectives are designed based on adolescents of SAARC countries (India, Bhutan, and the Maldives)

The prime purpose of the understudy is to explore the influence of pandemics on adolescent leisure activities.

The computable objectives of the proposed study are

- i. To investigate the variation in leisure activities of adolescents pre and post lockdown due to pandemic
- ii. To study the time spent by adolescents in leisure activities
- iii. To study the regression model in context to health problems
- iv. To study the health problems associated with adolescents of different countries

HYPOTHESIS

The Hypotheses designed based on objectives are tested at a 95% confidence level

- i. There will be statistically no significant difference in leisure activities during unlocking and lockdown
- ii. The regression model is not significant, in explaining health problems during the lockdown.

METHODOLOGY

Methodology in any study provides the modus-operandi of the research. It starts right from data collection; to the final step of data analysis. I have collected data through online and offline modes, according to the feasibility of the data.

Area of Study:

The adolescent studying in Grade 12th from India, Bhutan, and the Maldives has been selected for the study.

Population:

Adolescents (10-19) years are part of the population. According to UNICEF 2019, report nearly 350 million adolescents resides in South Asian countries is the part of the population for the proposed study

Sample & Sampling Techniques:

The study is a cross-cultural study of adolescents from India and its neighboring countries Maldives and Bhutan. The study used two-stage stratified sampling; in the first stage the sample was selected on a geographical basis, three states were selected from India; Uttar Pradesh and Uttarakhand from the North and Central Himalayan region and Madhya Pradesh from the Central part and school type/medium; Government (Kendriya Vidyalaya School) affiliated to CBSE Board were selected from India, Cambridge Board from the Maldives and Bhutan Higher Secondary Examination Certificate (BHSEC) from Bhutan. In the second stage, adolescents studying in senior secondary school (Grade 12th) were selected; one school was randomly selected from every region; it means three schools from India and one-one school from the neighboring countries. 161 students from three schools of India and 48 students from one school of the Maldives and 46 students from one school of Bhutan has been selected, overall 255 students has been selected for the study.

Respondent:

Adolescents studying in Grade 12th between the age group of 15-18 years are the specific respondents. Adolescents from SAARC countries; India, Bhutan, and the Maldives are the part of the study, selected from the five schools of these countries.

Tools:

The study used the questionnaire Leisure Interest Measure (LIM by Beard and Ragheb, 1980) short scale was used and a structured key information list for studying smartphone usage patterns (SPUP) by teens.

Schedule:

The study collected data before lockdown (BLD) in hard copies by interacting with students individually in their natural settings; classrooms during the month of Jan.-March 2020 whereas after lockdown (ALD) responses are collected in soft copy through Google Forms between (01 April-15 Sept. 2020).

Variables:

The understudy explore the facts related to COVID-19 and its impact on adolescent's leisure activities

Dependent Variable- Leisure Activities, Physiological and Psychological Health Problem

Independent Variable- Sex, Time spend SNS, Environment

Mediating Variable- COVID-19

Concurrent Variables:

Age, Income, Financial Status, Culture, Geographical Location, Religion, etc. all these variables are considered to be controlled during the study

Scoring:

In the case of LIM, the responses of the subjects were assigned numerical values or arbitrary

weights (as Likert terms it), ranging from 1 to 3; Never True as 1, Some What True as 2, and Always True as 3. 12 Items were selected from six different areas, so a total score of the short scale, the maximum score will be 36 and minimum score will be 12, information is given in the given table: 5 minutes was allotted for answering the LIM.

Table 1: Scoring the Test Items

Items	AREA OF ITEMS						TOTAL
	Reading	Physical	Outdoor	Artistic	Social	Service	
Items	1	02	02	02	03	02	12
Score	03	06	06	06	09	06	36

Thus, the total weighted score lays between 32-36, indicating 'most favorable', 27-32 mild favourable 22-27; neutral, 17-22; mild unfavorable and 12-17 indicates most unfavorable leisure interest.

In the case of collecting responses for the SmartPhone usage pattern (SPUP), the scoring against responses is given from 1-5 as options are given.

Design:

The quasi-experimental design includes both qualitative and quantitative techniques. The study tries to explore the changes during unlocking and lockdown due to COVID19 and its effects on adolescents' health, leisure interest, and other activities. The idea of considering Unlock as a Pre-test and Lockdown as a Post-test was clicked in my mind from one of my previous studies for studying the effectiveness of mathematics toolkit called 'Sampark' on students achievement and effectiveness of mathematics pedagogy called IMPACT (Sharma, A.& Singh, S.S., 2018).

Analysis:

Paired t, Multiple Regression, and other tests are used with the help of SPSS-23, even percentage bases are used, for analyzing the data, to study the change in leisure activities of adolescents which affected their leisure patterns during the pandemic.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

I. Paired Sample T-Test

Paired Samples Statistics

		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	Leisure Interest_ Unlock	26.3490	255	4.20439	.26329
	Leisure Interest_ Lock	25.3176	255	2.92375	.18309

Paired Samples Correlations

		N	Correlation	Sig.
Pair 1	Leisure Interest_ Unlock & Leisure Interest_ Lock	255	.730	.000

Paired Samples Test

		Paired Differences	t	df	

	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				Sig. (2-tailed)
				Lower	Upper			
Leisure Pair 1 Interest_Unlock - Leisure Interest_Lock	1.03137	2.87519	.18005	.67679	1.38596	5.728	254	.000

Paired Sample Statistics table shows that Leisure Interest has been declined during the lockdown as the mean during unlock was 26.3490 it declines to 25.3176 during lockdown it reflected that adolescent's interest has been shifted to another direction. Paired Samples Correlations between the group is .730 which shows a moderate degree positive correlation between the group whereas in the table Paired Sample Test, p value= 0.000 which is less than significant value 0.05, statistically significant difference exists. *Null hypothesis rejected.*

H₁: There is statistically significant difference in leisure activities during unlocking and lockdown

II. Multiple Regression

Variables Entered/Removed^a

Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	Time SNS-LD, Leisure Interest- LD, SEX ^b		Enter

a. Dependent Variable: Health Prb-LD

a. All requested variables entered.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.512 ^a	.262	.253	.40578

a. Predictors: (Constant), Time SNS-LD, Leisure Interest- LD, SEX

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	14.655	3	4.885	29.668	.000 ^b
	Residual	41.329	251	.165		
	Total	55.984	254			

a. Dependent Variable: Health Prb-LD

b. Predictors: (Constant), Time SNS-LD, Leisure Interest- LD, SEX

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		

	(Constant)	-.616	.249		-2.468	.014
1	SEX	.029	.052	.030	.551	.582
	Leisure Interest- LD	.005	.009	.033	.599	.550
	Time SNS-LD	.374	.040	.509	9.372	.000

According to the first table Variable Entered, three variables; Sex, Leisure Interest-LD, and TSNS-LD had been taken as a group of predictor variables whereas Health Problem-LD was considered as criterion or DV. Multiple Regression is used to study the effects of the group on the DV. In the table of Model Summary, the value of R= .512 shows a positive correlation between DV and IV in the regression model. The value of R square was .262; it explains the proportion of variance explained by the IVs in the regression model, i.e. the group accounts for 26% of the variance in DV. R² measured the amount of variance in the DV that IV accounts as a predictor for when taken as a group. Adjusted R square =.253, explanatory power of the regression model that contains different numbers of predictors, it always slightly less than R².

ANOVA table takes all the predictors as a group, p value= 0.00, which is below (α) < 0.05, it means that the Regression model is well fitted, as, R² is considerably greater than 0.00 predictors can measure the considerable degree of variance in DV; Health Problem-LD. Thus it shows that the **Regression model** is significant, which results in that the *null hypothesis being rejected*. The overall regression model is significant. When the study considers all three predictors together as a group they predict DV; Health Problem-LD significantly.

In **Table2** of Coefficients, here all three predictors are taken independently

Table 2; Predictors and Results

Predictors	p-value	Result
Sex	0.582 (greater than α value; 0.05)	Not Significant Predictor
Leisure Interest-LD	0.550 (greater than α value; 0.05)	Not Significant Predictor
Time SNS-LD	0.000 (less than α value; 0.05)	Significant Predictor

Only Time SNS-LD explains uniquely a significant amount of variance in DV whereas Sex and Leisure Interest-LD are not the significant predictor of DV; Health Problem-LD. It reflects that time spent on social networking sites during lockdown predicted the health problem during lockdown very efficiently.

III. Other Facts:

The other interesting facts related to the study are discussed under the following points:

- a. In the case of Leisure Interest Measure (LIM) which was collected during unlocking in hard copy include **29** items whereas during lockdown short form of that questionnaire was used, responses were collected through Google Forms; specifically from **six** different areas of interest which include only **12** items who has high correlation (component). It was observed that item in which students scored less during unlock, shows maximum score during the lockdown, especially in the Social segment where maximum adolescents responded 'Always True' against all three items, which reflects their interest in social activities, adolescents showed less interest in physical and outdoor activities during the lockdown and scored less against such items., which shows their upswing in behaviour.

It was quite observed that responses collected through Smart Phone Usage Pattern (SPUP) the time spent on SNS during unlocking to lockdown have been increased which reflects that adolescents

interest towards socialising with the help of digital technology. Digital technology usage was seen quite high in Maldivian adolescents followed by Indians and lastly Bhutanese. Facebook and WhatsApp was quite popular online communication platform used by adolescents, on average it was seen that during lockdown Maldivians spend 3: 167 hours, Indians spend 3:131 hours and Bhutanese spend 2: 243 hours on social networking sites. According to a report in 2019, there were 3.5 billion social media users globally, as far as India was concerned in 2018, there were 326.1 million users which will be expected to reach 448 million by 2023. (Clement J., 2019). According to Digital 2019, Global Digital Year Book by Simon Kemp, the report showed the average amount of time per day spent by Indians on the internet; surfing via mobile phone 03:43 hours and through computers (desktops, laptops or tablet) 04:03 hours whereas social media usage via any device, 2: 32 hours. The world's most visited websites as per the report by Hootsuite; Google stands first, as far as social networking sites were concerned Facebook stands third, Twitter, seventh, and Instagram, tenth. Mobile social media growth rankings are concerned India ranked second with an absolute increase of +60 million users and a growth rate of +26%. Based on monthly active users visiting social platforms Facebook with 2,271 million stands first with 1500 million users WhatsApp stands third.

- b. Based on the above study Indian nearly 66.46 %, 72.92% Maldivian, and 65.22% of Bhutanese adolescents claimed that they were suffering from health problems during the lockdown, due to excessive use of digital technology. The physiological and psychological problems discussed by adolescents of different countries can be highlighted with the help of the given table.

Table 3: Health Problems (Physiological / Psychological)

Country	Physiological	Psychological	Boys	Girls
India	Headache, Eyes	Tension, Anger, Suicidal Ideas	Head Ache, Tension, Suicidal Ideas	Eyes, Anxiety Short time Anger
Maldives	Headache, Eyes, Back pain and Digestion	Depression, Tension, Anger, Suicidal Ideas	Head Ache, Depression, Suicidal Ideas	Eyes, Anxiety
Bhutan	Back Pain, Digestion	Tension, Anxiety	Back Pain, Muscle Pull, Stress	Back Pain, Fear

Health problems were quite obvious amongst Indian and Maldivian adolescents whereas it was found slightly in Bhutanese, it may be due to the healthy lifestyle adopted by them, geographical locations, food culture, culture, environmental factors and maybe several other factors which played an important role in their lifestyle, which requires more research should be conducted in such area which is untouched in the existing study, maybe new unexplored facts can be tap out by conducting such exercise. Most of the adolescents, mainly from India and Maldives kept their cell phones with them while sleeping, the reason behind it they claimed, that they regularly check their cellphone updates, late in the night and even put alarms in their cellphones to get up early but it was seen that most of the adolescents get up late during lockdown it reflects their laziness and their late-night activities.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

With the advent of technology, lifestyle patterns, youth culture, traditional activities are being replaced due to the effusion of digital leisure in their life. It was found that Americans and European youths have a similar exercise of leisure time like exclusive groups of Indian adolescents who are quite different from the rural matrix of India (Saraswathi and Larson, 2002). Now the question arises of how we overcome the problem of digital dependency, and 'screen addiction', among adolescents which you can say is the boon or bane of such insurgency COVID-19. The best plausible solution or you can say suggestion to such problem is that despite these divergent views and so-called generation gap, parents should try to bridge the gap with their children by regular talking and discussing their scholastic, non-scholastic and leisure time activities, especially about their digital activities; online friends and other social interaction activities in a friendly manner, so that children can share their online screen activities with them. Parents should discuss the drawbacks of such technology with adolescents and suggest they use it for a specified period; otherwise, it will affect them in all spheres right from their academic to physical and psychological arena. The theme of the study is that parents try to be in the good books of their kids, COVID-19 provide them an opportunity to interact with them and understand their emotions and feelings, what they want from them, try to read their heart, parents try to improve their image in their sibling's eye and be the best friends of them, they should discuss the events of their school life and mistakes they had made in their life and realise them that they wouldn't make such mistakes after all they are their well-wishers. Overall the gist is, that parents try to manage their time and spend most of it with their offspring, involving them in indoor games, watching inspirational movies, cooking, gardening, gossiping, and even taking their lectures time to time, it means there will be a perfect schedule for every activity in a day and it will carry out even after total lockdown, inculcating good habits will take time, it will be panic also but such practices will change the life of an individual and COVID-19 provides such platform to break the rudimentary concept and think in a novel way with such ignited generation, even parents will learn a lot of thing from the younger ones, it will going to be quite a good and interesting experience for all the generations; right from childhood to old aged. Learning is the part of life, grasp it, COVID-19 has provided such opportunity, because family is one of the most important parts of our life, after all, we live and die for our family, let's experiment with our kids and be their true friend so that they share each and everything with us, this will be going to be a thrilling experience for the parents and it will force the psychologist to think from this angle.

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